

Research Note

Comparison of Antimicrobial Resistance of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* Isolated from Humans and Chicken Carcasses in Poland

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ABSTRACT

Campylobacter-associated gastroenteritis remains an important cause of morbidity worldwide, and some evidence suggests that poultry is an important source of this foodborne infection in humans. This study was conducted to analyze the prevalence and genetic background of resistance of 149 *Campylobacter jejuni* and 54 *Campylobacter coli* strains isolated from broiler chicken carcasses and from stool samples of infected children in Poland from 2003 through 2005. Nearly all isolates were susceptible to macrolides and aminoglycosides. The highest resistance in both human and chicken strains was observed for ciprofloxacin (more than 40%), followed by ampicillin (13 to 21%), and tetracycline (8 to 29%). Resistance to ampicillin and tetracycline rose significantly between 2003 and 2005. Slight differences in resistance between human and chicken isolates indicate that although chicken meat is not the only source of *Campylobacter* infection in our population, it can be involved in the transmission of drug-resistant *Campylobacter* strains to humans.

Campylobacter jejuni and *Campylobacter coli* are important causes of foodborne gastroenteritis in humans in many developed countries (2, 7, 24). Surveillance data on human campylobacteriosis in Poland are limited. However, the results of a 6-year study in Polish children with diarrhea revealed that the incidence of *Campylobacter* infections exceeded that of salmonellosis (32). Campylobacteriosis is often associated with handling of raw poultry or eating of undercooked poultry meat (4). Cross-contamination of raw poultry to other ready-to-eat foods via the cook's hands or kitchen utensils also has been reported (27). Campylobacteriosis is generally a self-limiting disease. However, in cases of severe or extraintestinal infections and in immunocompromised patients, antibiotics may be required. Erythromycin is the usual drug of choice for the treatment of *Campylobacter* infections (2). However, fluoroquinolones, gentamicin, and tetracycline also are clinically effective in treating *Campylobacter* infections when antimicrobial therapy is needed (2, 8, 24).

In many studies, a significant rise in resistance to fluoroquinolones, tetracycline, and erythromycin has been demonstrated in *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates (1, 15, 21, 22, 31, 34, 35). Increasing resistance is probably partly due to the wide use of these antimicrobials in veterinary medicine, especially in poultry (9, 10, 15, 40). In Poland, flavomycin

and avilamycin have been used as growth promoters in poultry farming operations, but this procedure was banned in 2006 according to the European Community 90/167/EEC directive (11). However, antimicrobials such as tylosin, tiamulin, lincomycin, amoxicillin, ampicillin, and tetracyclines can be used in medicated feed (6, 13).

The most common mechanism of high-level quinolone resistance in *Campylobacter* spp. is associated with a mutation in the quinolone resistance-determining region at position 86 in the *gyrA* gene (14). The most frequently observed molecular mechanism of tetracycline resistance is the production of Tet(O), a ribosomal protection protein. The *tet(O)* gene is often associated with conjugative plasmids. However, this gene also can be chromosomally located (12). The high-level resistance to erythromycin is mediated by mutations in domain V of the 23S rRNA gene at positions 2074 and 2075 (38).

The aim of this study was to compare the prevalence and genetic background of antimicrobial resistance in Polish strains of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolated from chicken carcasses and children to determine whether there was a link between these strains.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Samples of 130 broiler chicken carcasses were obtained from selected supermarkets in Warsaw. Stool samples from 946 children with diarrhea were obtained from three large pediatric hospitals in Warsaw. All samples were collected from 2003 through 2005.

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Isolation of *Campylobacter* spp. from chicken meat was performed according to the International Organization for Standardization guideline 10272 (20). After initial bacterial characterization by phase-contrast microscopy, Gram staining, catalase and oxidase production, and growth at 25 and 42°C, suspected colonies were confirmed as *C. jejuni* or *C. coli* using the PCR method with specific primers (33). Isolation and identification of human *Campylobacter* strains were performed according to World Health Organization recommendations (17) and confirmed by the PCR assay (33). All *Campylobacter* isolates were maintained in 20% glycerol in *Brucella* broth at -70°C for subsequent analysis.

C. jejuni and *C. coli* susceptibility to seven antimicrobials was determined by the Etest (AB Biodisk, Solna, Sweden) on Mueller-Hinton agar containing 5% sheep blood. Etests were used in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 h under microaerophilic conditions. The following CLSI interpretative criteria for the *Enterobacteriaceae* family were used as breakpoints for *Campylobacter* resistance: 16 mg/liter gentamicin and tetracycline, 32 mg/liter nalidixic acid, 4 mg/liter ciprofloxacin, and 32 mg/liter ampicillin. For erythromycin and azithromycin, an interpretative breakpoint for *Staphylococcus* spp. of 8 mg/liter was used (26). *C. jejuni* ATCC 33560 and *C. coli* ATCC 33559 were used as reference strains.

The *tet(O)* gene was detected by PCR assay (12). Thr-86-Ile mutations in the *gyrA* gene were identified by the mismatch amplification mutation assay PCR (MAMA PCR) as described elsewhere (41, 42); however, different reaction conditions were used: 94°C for 5 min for predenaturation followed by 35 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 54°C for 1 min, and 72°C for 1 min and a final extension at 72°C for 7 min. The presence of Thr-86-Ile substitutions was additionally confirmed by the PCR-restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) method (3). The PCR-RFLP method also was used for the detection of A2074C and A2075G mutations in the 23S rRNA gene (39). Isolates with discrepant phenotypic and genetic susceptibility results were subjected to direct sequencing of respective genes using DYEnamic ET Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit (GE Healthcare, Chalfont St. Giles, UK) on an Applied Biosystems 3730 automated sequencer (Applied Biosystems, Perkin-Elmer, Foster City, Calif.).

Statistical analysis. The resistance rates were compared using the χ^2 or V^2 tests.

RESULTS

During a 3-year study, 100 *Campylobacter* strains were isolated from 130 chickens, and 103 strains were obtained from 946 children. *C. jejuni* comprised 86.4% of human isolates ($n = 89$) and 60% of chicken isolates ($n = 60$). The remaining isolates were *C. coli*.

The results of antimicrobial susceptibility testing are summarized in Tables 1 and 2. All chicken *Campylobacter* strains and all but one human strain were susceptible to macrolides. Resistance to gentamicin was detected in three *C. jejuni* strains isolated from children and in one chicken strain. All gentamicin-resistant strains were obtained in 2005. The overall resistance to tetracycline in chicken *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* strains was 8.3 and 10%, respectively. The respective rates in human isolates were 15.7 and 28.5%. Tetracycline resistance in chicken isolates increased from 0% in 2003 to 17.3% in 2005 ($P = 0.01$). Ampicillin and ciprofloxacin had low activity against *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* strains regardless of their origin. From 2003 to 2005,

resistance to ampicillin rose from 8 to 35.5% ($P = 0.04$) in human isolates and from 5.8 to 30.4% ($P = 0.01$) in chicken isolates. High rates of ciprofloxacin resistance (>40%) were noted in both human and chicken isolates and did not change significantly during the study period. Cross-resistance to nalidixic acid and ciprofloxacin was found in all quinolone-resistant strains.

Resistance phenotypes are shown in Table 3. Resistance to quinolones was the predominant phenotype observed both in human (50%) and chicken (63.3%) isolates. The frequency of double resistance was significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) in human isolates (27 of 68 isolates, 39.7%) than in chicken isolates (7 of 60 isolates, 11.6%). Only two human *C. jejuni* isolates were simultaneously resistant to four antimicrobial agents.

All 149 *C. jejuni* and 54 *C. coli* strains were screened for molecular mechanisms of resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, and ciprofloxacin. The results of phenotypic and genetic analyses of resistance to tetracycline were fully concordant. All tetracycline-resistant isolates possessed the *tet(O)* gene. The results of macrolide susceptibility testing by Etests and 23S rRNA gene analysis were in agreement for all but one isolate. The only *C. jejuni* isolate resistant to erythromycin by the Etest method (MIC of 24 mg/liter) had no detectable A2074C or A2075G mutations in the 23S rRNA gene by either PCR-RFLP assay or direct sequencing. All *Campylobacter* isolates resistant to quinolones by the Etest had Thr-86-Ile mutations in the *gyrA* gene detected by MAMA PCR and PCR-RFLP assays. However, these mutations were also found by both molecular methods in two isolates phenotypically susceptible to ciprofloxacin (both MICs of 2 mg/liter) and nalidixic acid (MICs of 1 and 8 mg/liter). Both isolates were further confirmed by direct sequencing to contain Thr-86-Ile mutations.

DISCUSSION

In several studies, handling and consumption of poultry has been identified as important risk factors for *Campylobacter* infections in humans (4, 16, 18, 36, 37). The frequency of contamination of retail chicken meat with *Campylobacter* spp. has exceeded 80% in some countries (4, 36, 37). In a recent survey undertaken in Poland by the National Food and Nutrition Institute, 75% of chicken carcasses were contaminated with *Campylobacter* species (unpublished data). Microorganisms that colonize food animals or contaminate food products and are transmitted to humans via the food chain also can serve as a source of antimicrobial resistance genes for bacteria residing in the human gastrointestinal tract. Increasing *Campylobacter* resistance to antimicrobials is likely the result of the wide use of these agents in veterinary medicine and as growth promoters in animal farming operations. An estimated 50% of all antibiotic usage worldwide is in veterinary medicine (24). Use of quinolones, mainly enrofloxacin in veterinary applications, has been associated with the emergence of ciprofloxacin resistance in poultry and human strains of *Campylobacter* (9, 10, 15). In contrast, in countries where quinolones have not been used in food-producing animals, very low incidences (2%) of ciprofloxacin-resistant *Campylo-*

TABLE 1. MIC distributions of seven antimicrobial agents for 149 *C. jejuni* and 54 *C. coli* isolates^a

Antimicrobial agent (break-point, mg/liter)	Source	No. of occurrences at MIC (mg/liter) of:													
		0.006	0.012	0.016	0.023	0.032	0.047	0.064	0.094	0.125	0.19	0.25	0.38	0.50	0.75
AM (32)	Cj	H				2						3	2	1	2
		Ch					1		1	2	1	3	5	8	5
	Cc	H											2		
		Ch					1						1	2	4
EM (8)	Cj	H				1				2	1	4	10	12	21
		Ch								4	2	9	5	10	10
	Cc	H									2	3	1	3	2
		Ch					1	1		2	5	13	4	2	2
AZ (8)	Cj	H		15	9	14	9	10	4	8	6	5	2	3	2
		Ch		4	4	7	6	9	8	12	6	2		2	
	Cc	H		1		2	3	1	1	2	1	2	1		
		Ch			12	10	5	10			1				2
TC (16)	Cj	H		1	3		8	2	16	8	10	12	5	4	2
		Ch			4	2	6	12	10	4	6	3	2	3	2
	Cc	H			1	1		1	3	1	1	1	1		
		Ch		1		2	5	12	9	1			2		
CI (4)	Cj	H			1	1	3	4	6	6	7	2	3	1	
		Ch	2	1	3	3	7	4	7	2	2	3			
	Cc	H			1	1		1	2	2	1				
		Ch			1		4	2	1	4	1	3			
NA (32)	Cj	H													2
		Ch							1	1	1		1	2	4
	Cc	H													1
		Ch													2
GM (16)	Cj	H								1	3	3	1	13	22
		Ch						1		1		5	4	6	6
	Cc	H											2	1	4
		Ch									1	1		6	3

^a AM, ampicillin; Cj, *C. jejuni*; H, human; Ch, chicken; Cc, *C. coli*; EM, erythromycin; AZ, azithromycin; TC, tetracycline; CI, ciprofloxacin; NA, nalidixic acid; GM, gentamicin.

bacter have been observed (24). In Poland, quinolones are allowed for therapeutic use in veterinary medicine by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, which may explain the high resistance rates in *Campylobacter* strains analyzed in this study and in *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli* strains of poultry origin (19). The high prevalence of ciprofloxacin resistance in *Campylobacter* isolates obtained from children may result from transmission of poultry strains, because quinolones are used only occasionally in children, mainly in the treatment of cystic fibrosis.

Campylobacter spp. resistance to quinolones most frequently results from the Thr-86-Ile mutations in the *gyrA* gene (ACA→ATA in *C. jejuni* and ACT→ATT in *C. coli*) (28, 29). In this study, all isolates resistant to quinolones by the Etest possessed Thr-86-Ile substitutions. However, these mutations also were found in two isolates phenotypically categorized as quinolone susceptible (ciprofloxacin MIC of 2 mg/liter for both isolates and nalidixic acid MICs of 1 and 8 mg/liter). A similar phenomenon has already been observed. The *gyrA* Thr-86-Ile mutations were reported in *Campylobacter* isolates with a ciprofloxacin MIC of 2 mg/liter, which suggests that this concentration could be a more appropriate breakpoint for this agent (5, 29). Thr-

86-Ile substitutions also were found in isolates resistant to ciprofloxacin but fully susceptible to nalidixic acid (5).

A high prevalence of macrolide resistance in *Campylobacter* has been reported mainly in those European countries where tylosin has been used as an animal growth promoter (9). Among 203 *Campylobacter* isolates examined in this study, only 1 clinical *C. jejuni* strain had low resistance to erythromycin and azithromycin by the Etest, and this strain was simultaneously resistant to tetracycline, ciprofloxacin, and ampicillin. However, this strain did not contain either of the most frequent mutations in the 23S rRNA gene responsible for macrolide resistance, which suggests that resistance was associated with the efflux pump. Such a mechanism has been described in multidrug-resistant *Campylobacter* isolates with low-level macrolide resistance (30, 31).

An increase in the resistance of *Campylobacter* to tetracyclines has been observed in many countries. The prevalence of tetracycline resistance among *Campylobacter* isolates in the United States and Germany is close to 50% (23, 25), and in Spain it exceeds 70% (34). In this study, overall tetracycline resistance did not exceed 30%, and there were no significant differences in tetracycline resistance between

TABLE 1. Extended

No. of occurrences at MIC (mg/liter) of:																		No. (%) of resistant strains	
1.0	1.5	2.0	3	4	6	8	12	16	24	32	>32	48	64	96	128	192	256		>256
6	12	9	12	5	4	4	3	3	4	1		2		3	2			9	17 (19.1)
5	7	2	4	1	1	3	2	1					1	1				6	8 (13.3)
2				3	3	1						1						2	3 (21.4)
6	6	4	2	5	1		1			2				2				3	7 (17.5)
14	11	7	5						1										1 (1.1)
8	8	1	3																0
1	1	1																	0
2	2	4	2																0
	1						1												1 (1.1)
																			0
																			0
																			0
																			0
	1	1		1			1		1	1		3	5		1			3	14 (15.7)
1								2										2	5 (8.3)
		3		1									2	1	1				4 (28.6)
				1									2		1	1			4 (10.0)
1											52								53 (59.6)
		1									24								25 (41.7)
							1	1			6								8 (57.1)
		1						2			20								23 (57.5)
5	6	15	2	3	3														53 (59.6)
7	4	5	3	2	1	2	1						2						23 (41.7)
3		2																	7 (8 (57.1))
5		1	3	1		2	3					1	3		1				18 (23 (57.5))
25	4	6	1	1	1	3	2					2				1			3 (3.4)
12	8	6	3	2	1	3	1									1			1 (1.7)
3	2		1	1															0
9	7	5	1	1	2	1	3												0

human and chicken isolates. However, a significant increase in resistance was found during the last 3 years in chicken strains (but not in human isolates). This increase may be associated with the use of chlortetracycline and doxycycline in medicated feed for poultry and swine (6). The most important mechanism of tetracycline resistance in *Campylobacter* is the plasmid-mediated transfer of the *tet(O)* gene, which codes for the ribosomal protection protein (12). All our tetracycline-resistant isolates possessed the *tet(O)* gene.

Some authors have proposed the use of resistance pat-

tern in epidemiological investigations (31, 34, 35, 40). The most frequent resistance pattern observed in this study was the lack of susceptibility to a single agent, which was characteristic of 83.3 and 56% of chicken and human strains, respectively. Double resistance was detected three times more frequently in human strains than in chicken strains. Slight differences in resistance between human and chicken strains may indicate that chickens are not the only source of *Campylobacter* infection in our population. This finding is concordant with our previous findings of a different dis-

TABLE 2. Resistance of *Campylobacter* isolates of human and chicken origin to five antimicrobial agents in 2003, 2004, and 2005^a

Agent	Origin	% of resistant strains				P
		Overall	2003	2004	2005	
Erythromycin	Human	1.0	0	0	1.0	
	Chicken	0	0	0	0	
Gentamicin	Human	2.9	0	0	9.6	
	Chicken	1.0	0	0	3.2	
Ampicillin	Human	19.4	8.0	14.8	35.5	0.04
	Chicken	15.0	5.8	19.2	30.4	0.01
Tetracycline	Human	17.5	16.0	10.6	29.0	
	Chicken	9.0	0	11.5	17.4	0.01
Ciprofloxacin	Human	59.2	48.0	55.3	74.0	
	Chicken	58.0	56.0	76.9	60.8	

^a In 2003, 2004, and 2005, 25, 47, and 31 human isolates and 51, 26, and 23 chicken isolates, respectively, were obtained.

TABLE 3. Resistance phenotypes of chicken and human *Campylobacter* strains

Resistance pattern ^a	No. (%) of resistant chicken strains			No. (%) of resistant human strains		
	<i>C. jejuni</i> (n = 30)	<i>C. coli</i> (n = 30)	Total (n = 60)	<i>C. jejuni</i> (n = 60)	<i>C. coli</i> (n = 8)	Total (n = 68)
CI ^R	19 (63.3)	19 (63.3)	38 (63.3)	32 (53.3)	2 (25)	34 (50.0)
TC ^R	1 (3.3)	2 (6.3)	3 (5.0)	2 (3.3)	0	2 (2.9)
AM ^R	3 (10.0)	5 (16.6)	8 (13.3)	2 (3.3)	0	2 (2.9)
GM ^R	1 (3.3)	0	1 (1.6)	0	0	0
TC ^R + CI ^R	1 (3.3)	2 (6.3)	3 (5.0)	9 (15.0)	3 (37.5)	12 (17.6)
CI ^R + AM ^R	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	4 (6.7)	10 (16.6)	2 (25.0)	12 (17.6)
TC ^R + AM ^R	0	0	0	1 (1.6)	0	1 (1.5)
GM ^R + AM ^R	0	0	0	2 (3.3)	0	2 (2.9)
TC ^R + CI ^R + AM ^R	3 (10.0)	0	3 (5.0)	0	1 (12.5)	1 (1.5)
TC ^R + CI ^R + AM ^R + GM ^R	0	0	0	1 (1.6)	0	1 (1.5)
EM ^R + TC ^R + CI ^R + AM ^R	0	0	0	1 (1.6)	0	1 (1.5)

^a CI^R, resistance to ciprofloxacin; TC^R, resistance to tetracycline; AM^R, resistance to ampicillin; GM^R, resistance to gentamicin; EM^R, resistance to erythromycin.

tribution of some virulence markers in human and chicken *Campylobacter* strains (33).

This is the first Polish report of *Campylobacter* susceptibility in chicken meat strains. High resistance among these isolates to some antimicrobials may lead to increasing numbers of difficult-to-treat campylobacteriosis cases in humans. Therefore, constant monitoring of resistance is required in both human and poultry *Campylobacter* strains.

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